

Enfoque CLEWs para la mitigación de emisiones de GEI en cultivos de arroz y transición energética del transporte en Ecuador

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- Ecuador has an area of 256.370 km², which includes the continental region (coast, highlands and Amazon) and the insular part (Galapagos Islands).
- Maritime area of 1,358,440 km²

Context

- Ecuador's electricity matrix is highly dependent on hydropower (~56% installed capacity).
- Transport represents 54% of national energy demand.
- Rice cultivation is an important source of methane (CH₄) emissions.

Challenges

- Evaluating climate–energy–water–land interactions under future transition scenarios.
- Improving agricultural practices to reduce methane emissions from rice production.
- Managing the impacts of transport electrification on the power system.

Research Question

- How can integrated CLEWs modeling support greenhouse gas mitigation strategies in Ecuador's agricultural and energy sectors?
- What are the impacts of rice management improvements and transport electrification on emissions, electricity demand, land use, and water dependency in Ecuador?

Ecuador Reference Energy System

Scenarios

Using the OSeMOSYS Linear Programming Energy System Model the following scenarios were investigated:

Scenario Label	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
Baseline	Business-as-usual energy and agricultural system in Ecuador	Current electricity matrix dominated by hydropower; current rice management practices; projected energy demand growth maintained
Scenario 1 – NAMA Rice	Implementation of low-carbon rice management practices	1% annual yield increase; intermittent irrigation and improved fertilization; cumulative mitigation of -78.2 Gg CH ₄
Scenario 2 – Electric Vehicles	Progressive electrification of the transport sector	5 million electric vehicles by 2055; average travel distance of 20,000 km/year; electricity consumption of 15 kWh/100 km

Results

Rice cultivation area

Results

Results

Increase in demand due to EVs

Results

Power Plant Production

Main Findings

- NAMA rice practices reduced CH₄ emissions by >60%.
- Electric vehicle adoption increased electricity demand by ~15%.
- Hydropower remained the dominant electricity source.
- EV electrification increased total system emissions due to additional power generation needs.

Policy Insights

- Promote a national **NAMA Rice Ecuador** strategy to reduce CH₄ emissions through improved irrigation and fertilizer management.
- Diversify Ecuador's electricity matrix with solar, wind, and biomass to reduce hydropower dependence.
- Use the CLEWs Nexus approach to support integrated climate and energy planning.

Future Work

- Develop a detailed **NAMA Rice Ecuador** implementation framework and cost analysis.
- Ampliar el modelo para incluir sistemas de almacenamiento, infraestructura de transmisión y redes de carga para vehículos eléctricos.
- Incorporate climate variability and drought impacts into future hydropower modeling.

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